

The quality of anti-corruption education in Indonesian schools: adaptation of the Servqual method

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ABSTRACT

Anti-corruption education is a character education program that aims to instill anti-corruption values in students. The difference in the implementation of anti-corruption education as an autonomous subject provides different learning experiences for students. This research aims to measure the quality of anti-corruption education using the Servqual instrument. The Servqual instrument was developed and analyzed using confirmatory factor analysis (CFA). This research was conducted with an ex-post facto non-experimental design. The subjects involved were 156 students. Data analysis was carried out with the SmartPLS program. The results of CFA show that the instrument meets the fit criteria. Thus, the discriminant validity results have met the criteria, with a composite reliability (CR) value of 0.765 to 0.900. The results of the path analysis prove that three of the five Servqual constructs have a significant effect on the quality of anti-corruption education.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Anti-corruption education in Indonesia is a response to the low integrity of Indonesia's human resources. Referring to the 2021 Indonesian corruption perception index data, Indonesia is ranked 96th out of 180 countries with a score of 38 and the latest data for Indonesia will drop drastically in 2022 to rank 110th out of 180 countries with a score of 34 [1]. This condition is one of the reasons why anti-corruption education is important. School is the place of education that is most expected to maximize anti-corruption education for the younger generation. School is a place of education that is deliberately designed to build a learning community [2], [3]. Education in schools is an educational design for the future [4]–[6]. Thus, efforts to increase human resources in an anti-corruption context are one of the roles of school education [7].

The results of previous research contribute to increasing the effectiveness of anti-corruption learning in schools. Development of anti-corruption teaching materials [8], [9], models for implementing anti-corruption education [10], [11], development of anti-corruption education learning [12], and development of digital-based anti-corruption education learning media [13]. Various previous studies are efforts to increase the success of anti-corruption education in schools.

Many teachers complain about several obstacles to the implementation of anti-corruption education. The lack of facilities for teaching materials and the lack of facilities for instruments measuring anti-

corruption character are obstacles that many teachers complain about. The importance of the availability of teaching material products and instruments to measure anti-corruption attitudes is a primary need for implementing learning in the classroom [12], [14]. Schools even experience a lack of teachers who have expert competence in the field of anti-corruption education [15], [16].

Anti-corruption education is character education for children through the learning process. Several studies integrate anti-corruption education with religious education learning [17], [18]. This is in accordance with education policy in Indonesia, that anti-corruption education can be an insertion or autonomous subject. Anti-corruption attitudes and character are the final achievements expected from anti-corruption education policies in schools [19], [20]. Anti-corruption education is an educational policy to build students' character of integrity [21]. There are three aspects of measuring the success of eradicating corruption according to the Corruption Eradication Commission (Komisi Pemberantasan Korupsi/KPK), namely the integrity assessment survey (SPI), the anti-corruption behavior index (IPAK), and the corruption perception index (IPK). Based on data released by the KPK, the results of the SPI in 2021 obtained a score of 72.4 and in 2022 obtained a score of 71.94 [22]. Likewise, the IPAK in 2021 obtained a score of 3.88, and in 2022 it obtained a score of 3.93 [23]. Meanwhile, the IPK still refers to the data release [1] that Indonesia is ranked 96th out of 180 countries with a score of 38, and in 2022 it will fall to 110th out of 180 countries with a score of 34.

The Servqual instrument has been widely used by various previous studies to measure the service quality of a program or policy in education [24]–[26], health [27], [28], and even in the government sector [29]. The Servqual instrument is an instrument for measuring service quality with five dimensions measuring tangibles, reality, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy [30]. Therefore, evaluating the implementation of anti-corruption education is an activity that must be carried out to determine the quality of education implementation and for reasons to improve the implementation of anti-corruption education in the future.

Using the Servqual instrument in the education sector is the result of adapting the instrument according to needs [31]. Cuthbert pioneered the use of the Servqual instrument to measure the quality of educational services [32], [33]. This was followed by several studies adapting the Servqual instrument in the field of education [34]. The results of previous research prove that three of the five dimensions of Servqual have been proven to obtain significant scores in measuring student satisfaction with the implementation of education in schools [35].

The results of previous research prove that the Servqual instrument can be used to measure the quality of educational services in schools in several different aspects [33]–[35]. Therefore, the quality of anti-corruption education in Indonesian schools can be determined by assessing the quality of educational services using the Servqual method. The research questions (RQ) that arise in measuring the level of quality of anti-corruption education in schools are as: i) can the Servqual instrument be used to measure the quality of anti-corruption education? (RQ 1); and ii) what are the main constructs that structure the quality of anti-corruption education in schools? (RQ 2).

2. METHOD

2.1. Instrument construct

The instrument was developed based on the principles of the Servqual method by modifying it according to Servqual's anti-corruption education needs. The tangible dimension is adjusted to the scope of learning material aspects to describe the implementation of students' anti-corruption education learning. The dimensions and variables involved in this research can be seen in Table 1.

Table 1. Research hypothesis

Hypothesis (H)	Items	Dimensions
H1: the reality dimension has a significant effect on the quality of anti-corruption education in schools.	4	Reality
H2: the responsiveness dimension has a significant effect on the quality of anti-corruption education in schools.	3	Responsiveness
H3: the assurance dimension has a significant effect on the quality of anti-corruption education in schools.	5	Assurance
H4: the empathy dimension has a significant effect on the quality of anti-corruption education in schools.	3	Empathy
H5: the tangibles dimension has a significant effect on the quality of anti-corruption education in schools.	4	Tangibles

2.2. Data

High school students who have received anti-corruption education are asked to fill out a satisfaction survey regarding the implementation of anti-corruption education. Of the 180 students at the two schools, 156 students filled out the anti-corruption education satisfaction survey instrument completely and were ready for analysis. The number of respondents who meet the path analysis requirements is between 100-200

[36]. Research data was obtained from responses from grade 9 students aged 18 to 20 years. Therefore, these data can represent satisfaction with anti-corruption education at lower educational levels.

2.3. Analysis

SmartPLS is an analysis tool developed based on a composite-based analysis program. SmartPLS was developed as a structural equation model analysis tool based on partial least squares (PLS). SmartPLS is also effectively used for exploratory and confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) of existing constructs. Furthermore, path analysis can be carried out based on the results of the validity and reliability tests of the Servqual instrument that have been carried out. SmartPLS has several advantages because it can model several dependent and independent variables in multicollinearity conditions. This application is also able to produce more accurate predictions in cases of missing data [37].

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The CFA was carried out using covariance analysis using SmartPLS 3 to test construct validity and reliability. From the outer test results in Table 2, it can be seen that the outer loading score for each instrument is in the valid category. The outer loading of the Servqual instrument obtained a score between 0.765 to 0.900. This proves that the modified Servqual instrument meets the convergent validity requirements with the condition >0.70 [36].

In addition, the results of construct discriminant validity prove that the correlation between the same variables is always higher than the correlation between different variables. The next assumption is that a construct can be categorized as having good convergent validity if the average variant extract (AVE) is more than 0.5 [38]. The results of the discriminant validity test obtained AVE tangibles score of 0.798, reliability of 0.832, responsiveness of 0.794, assurance of 0.733, and empathy of 0.813. These results prove that the discriminant validity of the Servqual instrument is met.

Table 2. Loading factor

Construct	Item	Outer loading	CR
Tangibles	TG1	0.714	0.875
	TG2	0.858	
	TG3	0.838	
	TG4	0.774	
Reliability	RL1	0.847	0.900
	RL2	0.846	
	RL3	0.825	
	RL4	0.808	
Assurance	AS1	0.775	0.881
	AS2	0.783	
	AS3	0.809	
	AS4	0.727	
	AS5	0.769	
Empathy	AM1	0.823	0.854
	AM2	0.834	
	AM3	0.781	
Responsiveness	RS1	0.774	0.836
	RS2	0.814	
	RS3	0.793	
Satisfaction	ST1	0.728	0.765
	ST2	0.709	
	ST3	0.728	
Anti-corruption	AC1	0.761	0.860
	AC2	0.729	
	AC3	0.738	
	AC4	0.733	
	AC5	0.748	

Based on the measurement model, Figure 1 shows the results of identifying the relationship between the five Servqual factors between indicators and related factor dimensions. The model fits statistical test proves that the proposed model is acceptable. The matrix is determined with a coefficient scale of 1,000 for each Servqual indicator. The fixed weight t-statistic was significant ($p < 0.05$). This proves that the Servqual indicator in Figure 1 provides a good measure of the construct of each variable.

Figure 1. Path coefficient

Several criteria can be used to determine the suitability of the model structure based on path coefficients, composite reliability (CR), Cronbach’s alpha, and R square [39]. The criteria for model suitability in this research, the criteria score on the CR test is >0.700 which is in the very good category and <0.700 is in the poor category. Based on Table 2, it is known that CR shows that the CR score for the tangibles construct is 0.875, reliability is 0.900, assurance is 0.881, empathy is 0.854, and responsiveness is 0.836. The CR score proves that all constructs meet the reliability elements of the Servqual instrument. Therefore, all instrument constructs can be used in measuring the quality of anti-corruption education services in schools.

Based on the magnitude of the path coefficient, it is known that of the five constructs tangibles, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy, there are two constructs that do not have a significant effect on the quality of anti-corruption education in schools. As presented in Table 3, it is known that the constructs of empathy and responsiveness are two constructs that have a p-value>0.05. This is in line with previous research findings that in the education sector, not all dimensions in the Servqual instrument have a significant effect [35].

Table 3. Path coefficient

	SD	T statistics	P-value
Anti-corruption ->Satisfaction	0.034	21.073	0.000
Assurance ->Anti-corruption	0.079	4.610	0.000
Empathy ->Anti-corruption	0.068	1.078	0.153
Reliability ->Anti-corruption	0.074	3.693	0.000
Responsiveness ->Anti-corruption	0.067	1.676	0.062
Tangibles ->Anti-corruption	0.068	1.976	0.038

The results of this research show that the constructs of empathy and responsiveness do not have a significant effect on the quality of anti-corruption education. This means that teachers' empathy and responsiveness in anti-corruption character education do not have a significant influence on students. In contrast to previous findings, the assurance and tangibles constructs did not have a significant effect [35]. This is understandable because the scope of research is different.

Stodnick and Rogers adapted the Servqual instrument to measure the quality of classroom experience which is of course greatly influenced by the constructs of empathy and responsiveness. In contrast to these findings, the Servqual instrument has been proven to be effectively adapted to measure the quality of anti-corruption character education in schools. The two constructs of empathy and responsiveness do not have a significant effect on the quality of anti-corruption character education.

This finding is from Aldrup *et al.* [40] stated that empathy does not have a significant influence on teaching achievements and student outcomes. Other research results proved that teacher empathy can influence student learning motivation which can have an impact on learning outcomes [41], [42]. Students consider teacher empathy to be a relational relationship between teachers and students [43]. However, there is no consistent evidence about the relationship between teacher empathy and the quality of educational learning in schools [40].

The second finding proves that teacher responsiveness does not directly have a significant impact on the quality of learning in schools. Responsiveness can be a determinant of the quality of education if learning is carried out online [44], linguistic education in elementary schools [45], or learning in early childhood [46]. Meanwhile, at the upper secondary level, students need teachers more as facilitators in independent learning as a determining aspect of their success [47], [48]. Therefore, these findings prove that at the upper secondary education level, the teacher Responsiveness aspect does not have a very significant effect on the quality of anti-corruption education in schools.

This finding also proves that the Servqual instrument can be modified according to needs with different results. Tangibles, reliability, and assurance are three constructs that have a significant influence on the quality of anti-corruption character education. This is based on a P value score <0.05 . Furthermore, student satisfaction with the implementation of anti-corruption education is <0.05 . The modification of the Servqual instrument proves that through the three constructs tangibles, reliability, and assurance, anti-corruption education has a significant effect on student satisfaction scores in the implementation of anti-corruption character education in schools. This is proven by the R square tangibles score for anti-corruption is 0.135, assurance for anti-corruption is 0.364, and reliability for anti-corruption is 0.275. According to previous research, character education is greatly influenced by the reliability of the material, discipline in learning time, and the teacher's ability to teach the material [49]–[53].

4. CONCLUSION

Anti-corruption education is a form of anti-corruption character education in schools. Based on the results of measuring the quality of anti-corruption education in schools using the Servqual instrument, it is known that: i) the modified Servqual instrument can be used effectively to measure the level of quality of anti-corruption education programs in schools; and ii) three main constructs have a significant influence on the quality of anti-corruption education in schools, namely tangibles, reliability, and assurance. The recommendation from the results of this research is that there is a need for a periodic evaluation program on the quality of the implementation of anti-corruption education as a whole in Indonesia from the Ministry of Education through the education office in collaboration with the anti-corruption.

REFERENCES

- [1] Transparency International Indonesia, "Corruption perceptions index," 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://www.transparency.org/en/countries/indonesia>.
- [2] R. Walden, *Schools for the future*. Wiesbaden: Springer Fachmedien Wiesbaden, 2015.
- [3] A. Intasena and A. Poonputta, "Teacher preparation for local development project on students' self-conduct," *International Journal of Evaluation and Research in Education (IJERE)*, vol. 11, no. 4, pp. 1923–1929, Dec. 2022, doi: 10.11591/ijere.v11i4.22239.
- [4] M. S. Omar and M. I. Awang, "The learning environment as a predictor of higher order thinking skills," *International Journal of Evaluation and Research in Education (IJERE)*, vol. 12, no. 1, pp. 395–402, Mar. 2023, doi: 10.11591/ijere.v12i1.23959.
- [5] N. M. Zain, N. A. I. C. Mut, S. H. Norhan, and M. Marzukhi, "Are schools in Malaysia ready to open?" *International Journal of Evaluation and Research in Education (IJERE)*, vol. 11, no. 4, pp. 1959–1968, Dec. 2022, doi: 10.11591/ijere.v11i4.22670.
- [6] J. Shaturaev, "Indonesia: superior policies and management for better education (community development through education)." 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/357271101>.
- [7] P. Griffin, E. Care, and B. McGaw, "The changing role of education and schools," in *Assessment and teaching of 21st century skills*, Dordrecht: Springer Netherlands, 2012, pp. 1–15.
- [8] M. Zakiyah, P. K. Wulandari, and P. K. Dewi, "The development of an anti-corruption education module from a contextual perspective in higher education," in *Empowering civil society in the industrial revolution 4.0*, London: Routledge, 2021, pp. 52–58.
- [9] I. M. Suwanda, Sarmini, Listyaningsih, Murtiningsih, Misbakhun, and Chomariyah, "Anti-corruption education (PAK) teaching materials based on local character in social science subjects (IPS) to build anti-corruption culture for young generation in Surabaya," in *Proceedings of the 1st International Conference on Social Sciences (ICSS 2018)*, 2018, pp. 1557–1561, doi: 10.2991/icss-18.2018.324.
- [10] Sumaryati, Suyadi, Z. Nuryana, and A. W. Asmorojati, "Anti-corruption action: a project-based anti-corruption education model during COVID-19," *Frontiers in Education*, vol. 7, p. 907725, Jun. 2022, doi: 10.3389/educ.2022.907725.
- [11] K. Komalasari and D. Saripudin, "Integration of anti-corruption education in school activities," *American Journal of Applied Sciences*, vol. 12, no. 6, pp. 445–451, Jun. 2015, doi: 10.3844/ajassp.2015.445.451.
- [12] N. Indawati, "The development of anti-corruption education course for primary school teacher education students," *Journal of Education and Practice*, vol. 6, no. 35, pp. 48–54, 2015.

- [13] O. A. Astafurova, A. S. Borisova, E. V. Golomanchuk, and T. A. Omelchenko, "Anti-corruption education of public officers using digital technologies," *International Journal of Information and Education Technology*, vol. 10, no. 2, pp. 90–94, 2020, doi: 10.18178/ijiet.2020.10.2.1345.
- [14] Sarmini, I. M. Swanda, and U. Nadiroh, "The importance of anti corruption education teaching materials for the young generation," *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*, vol. 953, p. 012167, Jan. 2018, doi: 10.1088/1742-6596/953/1/012167.
- [15] I. D. Ishak, "Anti-corruption values civilization management model in the program of strengthening character education in public primary schools in Gorontalo regency," *International Journal of Science and Society*, vol. 1, no. 2, pp. 83–90, Sep. 2019, doi: 10.54783/ijssoc.v1i2.21.
- [16] G. K. Ratih, A. Iriani, and Y. Dwikurnaningsih, "Kindergarten teachers training in integrating anti-corruption education through storytelling and game," *Jurnal Obsesi: Jurnal Pendidikan Anak Usia Dini*, vol. 6, no. 3, pp. 1628–1639, Oct. 2021, doi: 10.31004/obsesi.v6i3.1806.
- [17] Suyadi, Z. Nuryana, and A. W. Asmorojati, "The insertion of anti-corruption education into Islamic education learning based on neuroscience," *International Journal of Evaluation and Research in Education (IJERE)*, vol. 10, no. 4, pp. 1417–1425, Dec. 2021, doi: 10.11591/ijere.v10i4.21881.
- [18] K. Harto, "Religion based-anti-corruption education (an effort to strengthen nation's character)," *Al-Ulum*, vol. 14, no. 1, pp. 1–22, 2014, [Online]. Available: <https://journal.iaingorontalo.ac.id/index.php/au/article/view/226/186>.
- [19] S. Al-Fatih, "Darus as an anti-corruption education," *Asia Pacific Fraud Journal*, vol. 3, no. 1, pp. 117–124, 2018, doi: 10.21532/apfjournal.v3i1.66.
- [20] J. A. Dewantara *et al.*, "Anti-corruption education as an effort to form students with character humanist and law-compliant," *Jurnal Civics: Media Kajian Kewarganegaraan*, vol. 18, no. 1, pp. 70–81, Apr. 2021, doi: 10.21831/jc.v18i1.38432.
- [21] A. R. Assegaf, "Policy analysis and educational strategy for anti corruption in Indonesia and Singapore," *International Journal of Asian Social Science*, vol. 5, no. 11, pp. 611–625, 2015, doi: 10.18488/ijournal.1/2015.5.11/1.11.611.625.
- [22] Jaringan Pencegahan Korupsi (JAGA) "Integrity assessment survey," (in Indonesian), Komisi Pemberantasan Korupsi (KPK), 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://jaga.id/jendela-pencegahan/spi?vnk=0a1cf58f>.
- [23] Badan Pusat Statistik (BPS-Statistics Indonesia), "Anti-corruption behavior index (IPAK) by dimension 2020-2022," (in Indonesian), 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://www.bps.go.id/indicator/34/635/1/indeks-perilaku-anti-korupsi-ipak-menurut-dimensi.html>.
- [24] M. A. Camilleri, "Evaluating service quality and performance of higher education institutions: a systematic review and a post-COVID-19 outlook," *International Journal of Quality and Service Sciences*, vol. 13, no. 2, pp. 268–281, Jun. 2021, doi: 10.1108/IJQSS-03-2020-0034.
- [25] F. L. Lizarelli, L. Osiro, G. M. D. Ganga, G. H. S. Mendes, and G. R. Paz, "Integration of SERVQUAL, analytical kano, and QFD using fuzzy approaches to support improvement decisions in an entrepreneurial education service," *Applied Soft Computing*, vol. 112, p. 107786, Nov. 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.asoc.2021.107786.
- [26] M. T. Sibai, B. BayJr, and R. dela Rosa, "Service quality and student satisfaction using Servqual model: a study of a private medical college in Saudi Arabia," *International Education Studies*, vol. 14, no. 6, pp. 51–58, May 2021, doi: 10.5539/ies.v14n6p51.
- [27] F. AlOmari, "Measuring gaps in healthcare quality using SERVQUAL model: challenges and opportunities in developing countries," *Measuring Business Excellence*, vol. 25, no. 4, pp. 407–420, Nov. 2021, doi: 10.1108/MBE-11-2019-0104.
- [28] A. Jonkisz, P. Karniej, and D. Krasowska, "SERVQUAL method as an 'old new' tool for improving the quality of medical services: a literature review," *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, vol. 18, no. 20, p. 10758, Oct. 2021, doi: 10.3390/ijerph182010758.
- [29] L. Ocampo *et al.*, "Public service quality evaluation with SERVQUAL and AHP-TOPSIS: a case of Philippine government agencies," *Socio-Economic Planning Sciences*, vol. 68, p. 100604, Dec. 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.seps.2017.12.002.
- [30] A. Parasuraman, V. A. Zeithaml, and L. L. Berry, "SERVQUAL: a multiple-item scale for measuring consumer perceptions of service quality," *Journal of Retailing*, vol. 64, no. 1, pp. 12–40, 1988.
- [31] F. Buttle, "SERVQUAL: review, critique, research agenda," *European Journal of Marketing*, vol. 30, no. 1, pp. 8–32, Jan. 1996, doi: 10.1108/03090569610105762.
- [32] P. F. Cuthbert, "Managing service quality in HE: is SERVQUAL the answer? Part 1," *Managing Service Quality: An International Journal*, vol. 6, no. 2, pp. 11–16, Apr. 1996, doi: 10.1108/09604529610109701.
- [33] P. F. Cuthbert, "Managing service quality in HE: is SERVQUAL the answer? Part 2," *Managing Service Quality: An International Journal*, vol. 6, no. 3, pp. 31–35, Jun. 1996, doi: 10.1108/09604529610115858.
- [34] B. M. Oldfield and S. Baron, "Student perceptions of service quality in a UK university business and management faculty," *Quality Assurance in Education*, vol. 8, no. 2, pp. 85–95, Jun. 2000, doi: 10.1108/09684880010325600.
- [35] M. Stodnick and P. Rogers, "Using SERVQUAL to measure the quality of the classroom experience," *Decision Sciences Journal of Innovative Education*, vol. 6, no. 1, pp. 115–133, Jan. 2008, doi: 10.1111/j.1540-4609.2007.00162.x.
- [36] J. J. F. Hair, W. C. Black, B. J. Babin, and R. E. Anderson, *Multivariate data analysis*, 7th ed. Pearson Prentice Hall, 2010.
- [37] W. W. Chin and G. Marcoulides, "The partial least squares approach to structural equation modeling," *Advances in Hospitality and Leisure*, vol. 8, no. 2, 1998.
- [38] J. C. Anderson and D. W. Gerbing, "Structural equation modeling in practice: a review and recommended two-step approach," *Psychological Bulletin*, vol. 103, no. 3, pp. 411–423, May 1988, doi: 10.1037/0033-2909.103.3.411.
- [39] H. Wold, "Partial least squares," in *Encyclopedia of statistical sciences*, Wiley, 2005.
- [40] K. Aldrup, B. Carstensen, and U. Klusmann, "Is empathy the key to effective teaching? a systematic review of its association with teacher-student interactions and student outcomes," *Educational Psychology Review*, vol. 34, no. 3, pp. 1177–1216, Sep. 2022, doi: 10.1007/s10648-021-09649-y.
- [41] S. Meyers, K. Rowell, M. Wells, and B. C. Smith, "Teacher empathy: a model of empathy for teaching for student success," *College Teaching*, vol. 67, no. 3, pp. 160–168, Jul. 2019, doi: 10.1080/87567555.2019.1579699.
- [42] J. Lee, Y. Lee, and M. H. Kim, "Effects of empathy-based learning in elementary social studies," *The Asia-Pacific Education Researcher*, vol. 27, no. 6, pp. 509–521, Dec. 2018, doi: 10.1007/s40299-018-0413-2.
- [43] H. W. Brackins, "Middle school students' perceptions of teacher empathy in Christian schools: a transcendental phenomenological study," *Middle School Journal*, vol. 53, no. 2, pp. 22–30, Mar. 2022, doi: 10.1080/00940771.2021.2022445.
- [44] N. Ndzinisa and R. Dlamini, "Responsiveness vs. accessibility: pandemic-driven shift to remote teaching and online learning," *Higher Education Research & Development*, vol. 41, no. 7, pp. 2262–2277, Nov. 2022, doi: 10.1080/07294360.2021.2019199.
- [45] L. M. Heikkola, J. Alisaari, H. Vigren, and N. Commins, "Linguistically responsive teaching: a requirement for Finnish primary school teachers," *Linguistics and Education*, vol. 69, p. 101038, Jun. 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.linged.2022.101038.
- [46] S. Byun, X. Zhao, C. K. Buettner, S. A. Chung, and L. Jeon, "Early childhood teachers' psychological well-being and responsiveness toward children: a comparison between the U.S. and South Korea," *Teaching and Teacher Education*, vol. 114,

- Jun. 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.tate.2022.103705.
- [47] E. Kormos, "Technology as a facilitator in the learning process in urban high-needs schools: challenges and opportunities," *Education and Urban Society*, vol. 54, no. 2, pp. 146–163, Feb. 2022, doi: 10.1177/00131245211004555.
- [48] E. C. van Dyk, G. H. van Rensburg, and E. S. J. van Rensburg, "The educator as facilitator of trust in the nursing education environment," *PLOS ONE*, vol. 17, no. 8, p. e0266240, Aug. 2022, doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0266240.
- [49] T. Taufiqurrahman and A. Nabilah, "Implementation of discipline culture in educational environment," *EduLine: Journal of Education and Learning Innovation*, vol. 3, no. 1, pp. 70–75, Jan. 2023, doi: 10.35877/454RI.eduline1515.
- [50] Z. Syapal, A. Amin, Alimni, Y. D. Citra, and P. A. Rivani, "A study of hard work and discipline character education in junior high schools," *Eurasian Journal of Educational Research*, vol. 99, pp. 127–142, 2022, doi: 10.14689/ejer.2022.99.008.
- [51] H. Yusuf, M. Syah, M. A. Ramdhani, and A. Hasanah, "The effect of interpersonal communication and teacher competence on the quality of character education and student learning achievement," *International Journal of Nusantara Islam*, vol. 8, no. 2, pp. 313–322, Dec. 2020, doi: 10.15575/ijni.v8i2.12663.
- [52] H. Hasbiyallah, M. Munadi, and D. Nurulhaq, "Character education model for high school students during the pandemic in terms of pedagogic competence and teacher personality," *International Journal of Instruction*, vol. 16, no. 2, pp. 1077–1094, Apr. 2023, doi: 10.29333/iji.2023.16257a.
- [53] M. T. Wuryani, R. Roemintoyo, and S. Yamtinah, "Textbooks thematic based character education on thematic learning primary school: an influence," *International Journal of Educational Methodology*, vol. 4, no. 2, pp. 75–81, May 2018, doi: 10.12973/ijem.4.2.75.

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